

Received XX Month, XXXX; revised XX Month, XXXX; accepted XX Month, XXXX; Date of publication XX Month, XXXX; date of current version 21 January, 2026.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/OJCOMS.2024.011100

Uplink and Downlink Slice-aware OFDMA Resource Allocation for Smart Factory Networks

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This work is supported by the 5GSmartFact project, which has received funding from the European Union's H2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant ID 956670. Also by the project 6-SENSES grant PID2022-138648OB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by FEDER-UE, ERDF-EU *A way of making Europe*, and the grants 22CO1/008248 and 2021 SGR 01033 (AGAUR, Generalitat de Catalunya).

ABSTRACT Smart factories require wireless networks capable of supporting diverse applications with stringent and heterogeneous quality of service (QoS) demands. Network slicing enables this by virtualizing resources into isolated slices optimized for specific service types. To effectively manage scarce radio resources and ensure seamless support for mixed-traffic industrial users, this paper proposes a suite of slice-aware resource allocation (RA) frameworks encompassing power and subchannel (SC) allocation for both uplink (UL) and downlink (DL) in industrial time-division duplexing (TDD)-orthogonal frequency division multiple access (OFDMA) networks. We transform diverse QoS constraints—latency, reliability, jitter, and throughput—into unified rate expressions enabling tractable convex optimization across three slice types: capacity limited (CL) for best-effort traffic, ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC) for mission-critical control, and time sensitive (TS) for deterministic periodic traffic. The framework incorporates dynamic TDD adaptation for asymmetric traffic patterns and admission control to manage congestion. The effectiveness of the proposed algorithms in reducing energy consumption while guaranteeing slice-specific QoS is validated using realistic industrial ray-tracing channels and extensive simulations.

INDEX TERMS Industry 4.0, network slicing, optimization, OFDMA, resource allocation, smart factory

I. INTRODUCTION

THE emergence of 5G and beyond networks promises to revolutionize industrial automation and immersive applications by supporting a diverse range of services on a unified infrastructure [1]–[4]. This evolution marks a transformative shift from rigid wired industrial networks toward flexible, high-performance wireless solutions that underpin Industry 4.0, where cyber-physical systems, industrial internet of things (IIoT) devices, and data-intensive applications—including autonomous robots, digital twins, and autonomous guided vehicles (AGVs)—demand deterministic and heterogeneous quality of service (QoS) guarantees [2] [4]. Such heterogeneity necessitates a departure from conventional one-size-fits-all resource allocation (RA) approaches, demanding instead dynamic strategies that en-

sure strict QoS for critical traffic while maximizing overall network efficiency.

Network slicing (NS) has emerged as the cornerstone technology to address these challenges. By allowing multiple logically isolated virtual networks (or 'slices') to co-exist in shared physical infrastructure, NS allows each slice to be customized for a specific application requirement [5] [6]. Thus, providing tailored network functionality while maintaining strict performance isolation through resource abstraction and dynamic orchestration [7] [8].

However, the realization of effective multi-slice co-existence in industrial environments, such as smart factories, faces several formidable challenges. First, the conflicting requirements across slice types create complex RA trade-offs. For example, ultra-reliable low-latency communica-

tion (URLLC) slices, supporting mission-critical applications such as emergency stop commands and robotic control, demand ultra-high reliability exceeding 99.999% with sub-millisecond latency bounds [9], meanwhile, time sensitive (TS) slices, carrying synchronized sensor data and coordinated multi-agent communications, require strict periodicity guarantees and bounded jitter [10]. Second, industrial wireless channels exhibit unique propagation characteristics that complicate resource management. The presence of metallic structures, dense machinery, and mobile obstacles creates highly dynamic and unpredictable channel conditions, necessitating adaptive RA mechanisms capable of rapid response without violating stringent slice requirements [11]. Third, the coupling between downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) transmissions in time-division duplexing (TDD) systems introduces additional complexity, as asymmetric traffic patterns vary significantly across slice types and time scales.

To address these challenges, we propose a comprehensive suite of slice-aware RA frameworks for UL and DL communications in multiuser TDD-orthogonal frequency division multiple access (OFDMA) systems. Our approach optimizes power allocation, subchannel (SC) assignment, and UL/DL slot configuration to meet the requirements of smart factory applications. The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- 1) Novel slice-aware RA frameworks for both UL and DL, formulated as joint power and SC allocation problems. The DL framework minimizes total transmission power subject to user-specific QoS constraints, while the UL framework employs power control to achieve equalized received signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) across users within tight power budgets.
- 2) A unified reformulation approach that transforms heterogeneous QoS constraints—including latency, reliability, jitter, and throughput requirements—into equivalent rate-based expressions. This reformulation enables the application of convex optimization techniques and facilitates computationally efficient solutions.
- 3) A power-aware admission control mechanism that dynamically redistributes user rates based on channel conditions and network load. This scheme preserves throughput for the capacity limited (CL) slice while simultaneously meeting the strict QoS requirements of the URLLC and TS slices.
- 4) A dynamic TDD slot allocation algorithm that adjusts UL/DL time splits in real time. This algorithm optimizes resource utilization and effectively balances traffic asymmetries in heterogeneous service environments with mixed traffic patterns.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews related works. Section III presents the system model, slice definitions, and channel model. Sections IV and V detail the DL and UL resource allocation problem

formulations respectively. Section VI introduces the admission control mechanism, while Section VII describes the dynamic TDD adaptation framework. Section VIII provides performance evaluation through simulations, and Section IX concludes the paper with final remarks and future research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

Conventional RA methods typically treat network resources as a monolithic pool, overlooking the service-specific granularity required by network slicing. In contrast, slice-aware RA entails fundamentally different approaches that dynamically allocate resources while maintaining distinct QoS profiles across multiple coexisting slices. This shift introduces significant complexity in resource management. In the literature, slice-aware RA solutions for OFDMA systems fall into two primary categories: optimization-based methods that leverage mathematical programming techniques, and learning-based approaches that employ artificial intelligence (AI)/machine learning (ML) algorithms for proactive RA.

Typically, optimization-based strategies model the RA problem as Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) or Nonlinear Programming (NLP) formulations, which effectively capture the interactions between disparate variables and diverse QoS constraints [12] [13]. Given the NP-hard nature of these problems [14], researchers have developed relaxation and decomposition techniques to enhance computational tractability, using heuristic and metaheuristic algorithms to achieve near-optimal solutions. Several studies focus on DL OFDMA systems. For example, [15] formulate joint power and resource block (RB) allocation under mixed numerology to minimize transmit power while maintaining QoS. This framework is extended in [16] through the integration of network function placement in open radio access network (O-RAN) architectures. In [17], a convexified multi-slice RA formulation balances enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB) throughput and URLLC latency requirements. Similarly, [18] employs chance-constrained optimization with successive convex approximation to support short-packet URLLC transmissions. Meanwhile, [19] uses Lyapunov drift-plus-penalty methods to optimize the sum rates per slice with power limitations, and [20] combine puncturing strategies with block coordinate descent for frequency and power allocation in OFDMA systems. The UL slice-aware RA problem is less addressed. In [6], UL RAN slicing for eMBB, massive machine type communication (mMTC), and URLLC services was investigated using heterogeneous non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) for improved spectral efficiency.

Although analytically robust, these optimization-based methods exhibit poor scalability under dynamic traffic and high user densities due to complex mathematical reformulations. Our approach overcomes this limitation by transforming all QoS constraints into equivalent rate constraints,

yielding tractable convex formulations and enabling real-time optimization.

Learning-based approaches, particularly deep reinforcement learning (DRL), have emerged as scalable alternatives that adaptively learn RA policies without requiring explicit traffic models. In OFDMA DL-centric studies, [21] introduces a two-tier actor-critic scheduler that combines interslice and intraslice RA. Industry 4.0-specific frameworks include [22], which uses multi-agent DRL with prioritized replay in digital twin systems to enhance fairness and QoS guarantees, and [23], which integrates federated learning and graph neural networks for predictive, slice-level resource management. Emerging 6G scenarios explore hybrid schemes: [24] combines prediction-assisted DRL with Lyapunov control for joint admission and power allocation, while [25] introduces preemptive DRL scheduling to balance URLLC reliability and eMBB throughput. Hierarchical DRL models, such as in [26], integrate local optimization and cloud policy learning for scalable RA.

Despite their adaptability, learning-based methods suffer from prohibitive training overhead, opaque decision-making, vulnerability to distribution shifts, and uncertain convergence—critical drawbacks for real-time deployment.

While prior works have advanced slice-aware RA for smart factory networks, they remain limited by computational complexity and generic use-case assumptions. Our framework addresses these gaps through three key innovations. First, unlike the approaches in [15]–[19] that rely on complex mathematical reformulations, we simplify the RA problem by translating all QoS constraints into tractable target rate expressions. Second, we define three slice categories—TS, URLLC, CL—aligned with industrial automation use cases specified by 3GPP and 5G-ACIA [9] [27]. Although [20] considers industrial networks, it overlooks periodic isochronous traffic vital for time-triggered control and synchronized actuation—explicitly supported in our TS slice. Third, existing studies typically optimize either UL or DL transmissions in isolation, while dynamic TDD approaches [28] focus solely on time-split optimization without considering slice-specific RA. In contrast, our framework jointly addresses both dynamic TDD configuration and multi-slice RA for smart factory applications. We adapt UL/DL time splits based on real-time traffic asymmetries and incorporate lightweight admission control that preserves mission-critical QoS through intelligent rate redistribution during network congestion.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a single-cell TDD-OFDMA system comprising one base station (BS) serving a set \mathcal{N} of N users and having a set \mathcal{K} of K available SCs. Each user belongs to a network slice with distinct QoS requirements, including data rate, latency, reliability, and jitter. A slice is defined as a logical network partition serving a group of users with similar QoS requirements, tailored to the characteristics of their

associated traffic type [29] [7]. Users are statically associated with one slice, and resource allocation is performed per slice to meet QoS targets while maintaining isolation. The packet arrival process for user i follows a Poisson distribution with rate ζ_i (packets/s). Packet lengths are exponentially distributed with mean \bar{L}_i (bits/packet), resulting in a bit arrival rate $a_i = \zeta_i \cdot \bar{L}_i$ (bits/s). Under these assumptions, the packet queues at the BS follow an M/M/1 model. The system architecture is shown in Figure 1.

To accommodate the diverse traffic requirements of industrial automation [9] [27], we defined three slice types:

- 1) *CL Slices*: support best-effort traffic without stringent QoS requirements, including file transfers, log uploads, and non-critical data services. Resources are allocated opportunistically from residual capacity, with aggregate throughput constrained by a slice-specific capacity limit C .
- 2) *URLLC Slices*: support mission-critical applications including real-time control, extended reality (XR) interfaces, and AGV coordination. These services generate asynchronous, latency sensitive traffic with short packets, subject to strict reliability constraints $\Pr(D_i > D_i^{\max}) < 1 - \gamma_i$, where D_i^{\max} and γ_i denote the delay limit and the reliability target, respectively, for a user i in a URLLC slice.
- 3) *TS Slices*: support periodic, isochronous traffic from applications like machine vision and closed-loop control. Fixed-size packets arrive at regular intervals aligned with the scheduling period T_{sp} , and require low bit error rate (BER) and strict latency and jitter bounds. We exploit this predictability by reserving dedicated time slots while optimizing SC allocation within them, with numerology chosen to match traffic periodicity for minimal overhead.

The RA framework must jointly allocate SCs and power across slices while ensuring QoS satisfaction and inter-slice isolation. URLLC slices receive priority scheduling for low latency and jitter, TS slices are served deterministically to prevent timing jitter, and CL slices utilize remaining capacity opportunistically.

The achievable rate for user i is upper-bounded by the Shannon capacity:

$$r_i = B \sum_{j=1}^K x_{ij} \log_2 \left(1 + \beta_i \frac{p_{ij} h_{ij}}{x_{ij} \sigma^2} \right), \quad (1)$$

where B is the SC bandwidth, h_{ij} is the channel gain on SC j , σ^2 denotes noise power (inclusive of interference), and $x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$ is the SC allocation indicator, with $x_{ij} = 1$ when SC j is assigned to user i . The modulation-specific factor β_i accounts for BER performance under M-QAM schemes [30], ensuring sufficiently reliable transmissions. The variable p_{ij} represents the average transmit power allocated to user i on SC j over the scheduling period T_{sp} . Since user i transmits on SC j only when $x_{ij} = 1$, the instanta-

neous power during active transmission is p_{ij}/x_{ij} , reflecting that the allocated power is concentrated over the occupied time-frequency resource. When $x_{ij} = 0$, no transmission occurs, and both average and instantaneous power are zero. The placement of x_{ij} in the denominator of (1) models this power concentration and preserves the Shannon rate expression, since the term evaluates to zero when $x_{ij} = 0$. Moreover, this formulation ensures joint concavity of r_i with respect to (p_{ij}, x_{ij}) , enabling convex optimization of SC and power allocation [31]. All parameters—packet arrivals, channel gains, and allocated rates—are implicitly evaluated within the scheduling period T_{sp} ; the explicit time index is omitted for notational simplicity.

To accommodate asymmetric traffic patterns, we adopt dynamic TDD that adaptively adjusts UL/DL time allocation based on real-time load conditions. In single-cell deployments, this approach enables flexible slot partitioning without interference concerns. Multi-cell scenarios, however, require coordination mechanisms to mitigate cross-cell interference arising from misaligned UL/DL configurations.

FIGURE 1. Illustration of DL/UL slice-aware resource allocation system.

We employ deterministic ray-tracing (RT) to model the wireless channel, as industrial environments present unique propagation challenges that statistical models cannot adequately capture. By leveraging precise geometric and material properties, RT accurately computes electromagnetic interactions—reflection, diffraction, scattering, and refraction—with factory equipment, yielding site-specific path loss, delay spread, and multipath fading characteristics [32]. This high-fidelity modeling is essential for validating RA under the extreme conditions imposed by metallic structures and dense machinery.

The RT channel model is implemented using Volcano Flex [33] [34], configured to trace up to two reflections and one diffraction (2R1D) per propagation path. The evaluation environment represents a $210 \times 97 \times 5$ m³ textile manufacturing facility, with analysis focused on areas containing

dense metallic storage racks that create challenging multipath conditions typical of industrial settings. Material electromagnetic properties follow ITU-R P.1238-7 specifications [35], while environmental parameters—rack dimensions, object heights, and clutter density—replicate realistic factory deployments, as discussed further in Section VIII.

The scheduling period satisfies $T_{sp} < T_c$, where T_c is the channel coherence time, ensuring that the channel remains approximately constant over each allocation interval. All users are assumed stationary, representing fixed industrial equipment at predetermined locations; channel variations arise primarily from environmental scatterers (e.g., moving personnel or machinery), whose dynamics occur on timescales of hundreds of milliseconds to seconds. Estimating $T_c \approx 0.423/f_D$ conservatively, where $f_D = vf_c/c$ is the maximum Doppler frequency associated with scatterer velocity v , even for $v = 3$ m/s at the carrier frequency considered, T_c remains well above T_{sp} , validating the quasi-static channel assumption.

Figure 2 illustrates the end-to-end algorithmic pipeline of the proposed framework, encompassing QoS-to-rate transformation, DL and UL resource allocation, admission control, and dynamic TDD adaptation. The subsequent sections detail each stage.

IV. DOWNLINK RESOURCE ALLOCATION

We propose two DL RA schemes: (i) differentiated power allocation (DPA), which jointly optimizes power using water-filling [36] [37]—and SC assignment to achieve optimal performance; and (ii) equal power allocation (EPA), which uniformly distributes power across SCs while optimizing the SC assignment.

A. DIFFERENTIATED POWER AND SUBCHANNEL ALLOCATION

The DPA problem minimizes total transmission power subject to user rate constraints:

$$\min_{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^K p_{ij}, \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } r_i \geq r_{o,i}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (2b)$$

$$p_{ij} \geq 0, \quad x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (2c)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N x_{ij} \leq 1, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (2d)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^K p_{ij} \leq P_{\max}^{\text{DL}}. \quad (2e)$$

Constraint (2c) enforces power non-negativity and binary SC assignment, constraint (2d) ensures each SC is assigned to one user at most, and constraint (2e) limits the total BS transmit power. $r_{o,i}$ in constraint (2b) denotes the target rate for user i , derived by transforming heterogeneous QoS constraints into equivalent rate requirements as follows.

FIGURE 2. End-to-end block diagram of the proposed slice-aware resource allocation framework.

For users in the URLLC slice, the delay constraint requires a rate that ensures $\Pr\{D_i \geq D_i^{\max}\} \leq 1 - \gamma_i$. Packets are served at TDD frame boundaries with period T_f , where each frame is partitioned into a transmission phase of duration ηT_f and an opposite-direction phase of duration $(1 - \eta)T_f$. The resource allocation (power and SC assignments) is recomputed every scheduling period $T_{sp} \gg T_f$, so that multiple TDD frames are served using each allocation decision.

As derived in the Appendix, the delay distribution comprises three components: (i) M/M/1 queuing delay, (ii) frame synchronization delay uniformly distributed over $[0, T_f]$, and (iii) TDD-induced delay from packets spanning multiple transmission phases. The resulting outage probability in (56) depends on the service parameter $\alpha_i = (r_{o,i} - a_i) / \bar{L}_i$ and the packing parameter $\omega_i = r_{o,i} \eta T_f / \bar{L}_i$, where ω_i quantifies how many average-sized packets fit within a single transmission phase. The minimum rate $r_{o,i}$ satisfying the reliability constraint is obtained by numerically solving (56) for $\alpha_i^{(TDD)}$, yielding:

$$r_{o,i} = a_i + \alpha_i^{(TDD)} \bar{L}_i. \quad (3)$$

When the URLLC slice also specifies a jitter constraint J_i , an additional rate requirement applies per (47), giving

the combined requirement:

$$r_{o,i} = a_i + \bar{L}_i \cdot \max \left(\alpha_i^{(TDD)}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{J_i^2 - T_f^2/12}} \right), \quad (4)$$

where γ_i , D_i^{\max} , and J_i denote the reliability target, maximum delay bound, and jitter bound, respectively; a_i is the packet arrival rate in bits/s and \bar{L}_i is the mean packet size. The jitter term arises from the variance of the frame synchronization delay, which contributes $T_f^2/12$ to the total delay variance. The formulation in (4) requires $T_f < D_i^{\max}$ to avoid outage probability saturation, and $J_i > T_f/\sqrt{12}$ for the jitter constraint to be feasible.

For users in TS slice with fixed packet size L :

$$r_{o,i} = L/T_f. \quad (5)$$

For CL slice users, the aggregate rate is constrained by the slice capacity C :

$$\sum_{i=1}^N r_i = C. \quad (6)$$

Since the CL slice imposes only an aggregate capacity constraint, individual user rate targets are initialized equally as $r_{o,i} = C/N_{CL}$, where N_{CL} is the number of CL slice users. These targets are subsequently redistributed by the

admission control mechanism (Section VI) based on channel-dependent power sensitivities.

Problem (2) is thus solved using Lagrangian dual decomposition in each scheduling period, enabling dynamic resource allocation across coexisting slices.

1) Lagrangian Dual Formulation

Relaxing x_{ij} to take continuous values in the interval $[0, 1]$, the optimization problem in (2) becomes convex and remains feasible, which can be solved using Lagrangian dual decomposition. We can rewrite (2) as $\min_{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}} \mathcal{L}$, where \mathcal{L} is the Lagrangian function given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} &= \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^K p_{ij} + \sum_{j=1}^K \mu_j \left(\sum_{i=1}^N x_{ij} - 1 \right) + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i (r_{o,i} - r_i) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\sum_{j=1}^K (p_{ij} + \mu_j x_{ij}) + \lambda_i (r_{o,i} - r_i) \right] - \sum_{j=1}^K \mu_j \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{L}_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}; \boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}) - \sum_{j=1}^K \mu_j. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

λ_i and μ_j are the dual variables for rate and SC allocation constraints, respectively.

2) Power Allocation

Solving $\partial \mathcal{L} / \partial p_{ij} = 0$ gives the optimal power allocation for the i -th user:

$$p_{ij}^* = x_{ij} \left[\frac{\lambda_i B}{\beta_i \ln 2} - \frac{\sigma^2}{h_{ij}} \right]^+, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (8)$$

where $[\cdot]^+$ denotes $\max(\cdot, 0)$.

3) Subchannel Assignment

To obtain the optimal SC allocation variables x_{ij} , we substitute (8) into $\mathcal{L}_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}; \boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu})$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}^*; \boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}) &= \sum_{j=1}^K x_{ij} \left(\left[\frac{\lambda_i B}{\ln 2} - \frac{\sigma^2}{h_{ij}} \right]^+ + \mu_j \right) + \lambda_i r_{o,i} \\ &\quad - \lambda_i B \sum_{j=1}^K x_{ij} \log_2 \left(1 + \left[\frac{\lambda_i B}{\ln 2} - \frac{\sigma^2}{h_{ij}} \right]^+ \frac{h_{ij}}{\sigma^2} \right) \\ &= \lambda_i r_{o,i} - \sum_{j=1}^K x_{ij} (\mu_{ij}(\lambda_i) - \mu_j), \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where we define the auxiliary function:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{ij}(\lambda_i) &= \lambda_i B \log_2 \left(1 + \left[\frac{\lambda_i B}{\beta_i \ln 2} - \frac{\sigma^2}{h_{ij}} \right]^+ \frac{h_{ij}}{\sigma^2} \right) \\ &\quad - \left[\frac{\lambda_i B}{\beta_i \ln 2} - \frac{\sigma^2}{h_{ij}} \right]^+. \end{aligned}$$

Since (9) is linear (affine) in x_{ij} , minimization over $x_{ij} \in [0, 1]$ yields:

$$x_{ij}^* = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \mu_{ij}(\lambda_i) > \mu_j, \\ 0 & \text{if } \mu_{ij}(\lambda_i) < \mu_j, \\ [0, 1] & \text{if } \mu_{ij}(\lambda_i) = \mu_j. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) is the solution to the relaxed problem. Note that we obtain binary values for the first two cases. For the boundary case $\mu_{ij}(\lambda_i) = \mu_j$, we adopt $x_{ij} = 1$ as a feasible solution, acknowledging a potential gap to optimality. The optimal SC allocation variable is thus $x_{ij}^* = 1$ if $\mu_{ij}(\lambda_i) \geq \mu_j$, and $x_{ij}^* = 0$ otherwise. This yields the assignment rule for SC j to user i :

$$i_j^* = \arg \max_i \mu_{ij}(\lambda_i), \quad \forall j. \quad (11)$$

4) Dual Problem

From (9) and the SC assignment rule in (10), we obtain:

$$\mathcal{L}_i(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}) = \lambda_i r_{o,i} - \sum_{j=1}^K (\mu_{ij}(\lambda_i) - \mu_j)^+, \quad (12)$$

and substituting into (7), the dual function becomes:

$$\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i r_{o,i} - \sum_{j=1}^K \left[\sum_{i=1}^N (\mu_{ij}(\lambda_i) - \mu_j)^+ + \mu_j \right]. \quad (13)$$

We proved in [29] that the optimal $\mu_j^* = \max_i \mu_{ij}(\lambda_i)$ minimizes the right term in (13), therefore:

$$\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i r_{o,i} - \sum_{j=1}^K \max_i \mu_{ij}(\lambda_i). \quad (14)$$

Since (14) is concave (the dual function is the point-wise infimum of a family of affine functions of λ_i), the dual variables $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ can be updated using the ellipsoid method [31], which offers fast convergence without requiring learning rate tuning. The subgradient of (14) is:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\lambda})}{\partial \lambda_i} = r_{o,i} - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} B \log_2 \left(\frac{\lambda_i B}{\beta_i \ln 2} \frac{h_{ij}}{\sigma^2} \right), \quad (15)$$

where $\mathcal{J}_i = \{j \in \mathcal{K} \mid i_j^* = i\}$ denotes the set of SCs allocated to user i according to (11), and the gradient term applies only when $\lambda_i > \frac{\sigma^2 \beta_i \ln 2}{B h_{ij}}$.

B. EQUAL POWER ALLOCATION

In the DPA strategy of Section IV-A, power is allocated to satisfy individual rate constraints, resulting in higher transmit power for cell-edge users and lower power for those near the BS. Although theoretically optimal in terms of power minimization, such power imbalance increases the disparity of received signal levels at the BS. Large received-power differences are known to aggravate near-far effects [38] and may stress the receiver front-end dynamic range, particularly due to finite analog-to-digital converter (ADC) resolution and quantization constraints [39].

To address these practical considerations, we propose EPA, which transmits uniform power p across all active SCs. Unlike DPA, which optimizes individual p_{ij} per user-SC pair, EPA jointly optimizes a single power level p and SC assignments \mathbf{x} . This simplifies RF front-end implementation and reduces nonlinear distortion effects associated with large instantaneous power variations [38]. Moreover, EPA reduces the disparity in per-SC transmit power levels and consequently narrows the range of received signal powers at the BS. While full mitigation of near-far effects would require signal-level modeling (e.g., ADC quantization and front-end nonlinearities), limiting received power spread is a necessary condition for reducing dynamic range stress in practical multiuser receivers [39], [40]. The EPA problem is formulated as:

$$\min_{p, \mathbf{x}} K \cdot p, \quad (16a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } r_i \geq r_{o,i}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (16b)$$

$$p \geq 0, \quad x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (16c)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N x_{ij} = 1, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (16d)$$

$$K \cdot p \leq P_{\max}^{\text{DL}}. \quad (16e)$$

The objective $K \cdot p$ represents the total transmit power across all SCs, and constraint (16e) enforces the BS power budget. Problem (16) is a mixed-integer nonlinear program (MINLP) due to the coupling between p and \mathbf{x} in the rate constraints. Moreover, the rate expression (1) yields a transcendental equation in p with no closed-form solution, necessitating numerical methods.

We solve (16) using the two-stage iterative procedure described in Algorithm 1. In the first stage, for a fixed SC allocation x_{ij} initialized from Section IV-A, a bisection search [41] determines the minimum uniform transmit power p^* that satisfies all rate constraints. Convergence of this stage is guaranteed, since each user rate r_i is monotonically increasing in p . In the second stage, to address the rate imbalances caused by heterogeneous channel conditions under EPA, an SC reallocation mechanism transfers subchannels from over-provisioned users to under-served users. After each reallocation step, the bisection search is repeated to compute the updated p^* corresponding to the modified x_{ij} . This process iterates until convergence or termination.

Although the bisection stage converges for any fixed SC assignment, the overall procedure does not guarantee monotonic power reduction, as certain channel realizations may induce oscillatory reallocation patterns between users. To ensure termination, Algorithm 1 enforces a maximum iteration limit I_{\max} and retains the best (lowest-power) feasible solution encountered across iterations, terminating early if no power improvement is observed over two consecutive iterations. In practice, convergence is consistently achieved within a few iterations.

Algorithm 1 EPA with Subchannel Reallocation

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1: Input: Initial  $x_{ij}$  (from DPA),  $r_{o,i}$ ,  $h_{ij}$ ,  $I_{\max}$ 
2: Output: Optimized  $p$ ,  $x_{ij}$ , achieved rates  $r_i$ 
3: Initialize:  $p_{\text{old}} \leftarrow 0$ ,  $p \leftarrow \infty$ ,  $p^{\text{best}} \leftarrow \infty$ ,  $x_{ij}^{\text{best}} \leftarrow x_{ij}$ ,
   tolerance  $\epsilon$ ,  $t \leftarrow 0$ 
4: while  $|p - p_{\text{old}}| > \epsilon \cdot p$  and  $t < I_{\max}$  do
5:    $p_{\text{old}} \leftarrow p$ 
6:   for each user  $i = 1, \dots, N$  do
7:     Find  $p_i$  via bisection such that  $r_i \geq r_{o,i}$ 
8:   end for
9:    $p \leftarrow \max_i p_i$  ▷ EPA constraint
10:  if  $p < p^{\text{best}}$  then ▷ Track best solution
11:     $p^{\text{best}} \leftarrow p$ ,  $x_{ij}^{\text{best}} \leftarrow x_{ij}$ 
12:  else if  $p \geq p_{\text{old}}$  then ▷ Oscillation detected
13:     $p \leftarrow p^{\text{best}}$ ,  $x_{ij} \leftarrow x_{ij}^{\text{best}}$ 
14:    break
15:  end if
16:  Compute  $r_i$  using  $p$  for all  $i$  via (1)
17:  for each user  $i$  do ▷ SC reallocation
18:     $\Delta r_i \leftarrow (r_i - r_{o,i})/r_i$  ▷ Relative rate excess
19:  end for
20:   $I \leftarrow \text{Sort}(\Delta r_i, \text{descending})$ 
21:   $u_h \leftarrow I[1]$ ,  $u_l \leftarrow I[N]$  ▷ User with highest/lowest
   excess
22:   $\mathcal{J}_h \leftarrow \{j : x_{u_h,j} = 1\}$  ▷ SCs assigned to  $u_h$ 
23:   $N_r \leftarrow \max(|\mathcal{J}_h| \cdot \Delta r_{u_h}, 1)$  ▷ SCs to reallocate
24:   $\mathcal{J}_{h,s} \leftarrow \text{Sort}(h_{u_h,j}, \text{ascending})$  ▷ Sort by channel
   gain
25:   $\mathcal{J}_r \leftarrow$  first  $N_r$  elements of  $\mathcal{J}_{h,s}$  ▷ Worst channels
   of  $u_h$ 
26:  for  $j \in \mathcal{J}_r$  do
27:     $x_{u_h,j} \leftarrow 0$ ,  $x_{u_l,j} \leftarrow 1$  ▷ Transfer SC to  $u_l$ 
28:  end for
29:   $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
30: end while

```

The proposed two-stage approach balances computational efficiency with near-optimal performance while avoiding the complexity of solving the full MINLP.

V. UPLINK RESOURCE ALLOCATION

In the UL, users transmit independently and may arrive at the BS with widely varying received powers due to path loss and fading. This near-far imbalance can stress the BS receiver dynamic range, as large received-power disparities risk degrading weak-user signals due to finite ADC resolution [38], [39]. To limit this received-power spread, we adopt a power control policy that equalizes the received SNR across users by enforcing a common received SNR target θ that each user must meet, rather than allowing strong users to dominate the received power range. The UL power control and SC

allocation problem is formulated as:

$$\min_{\theta, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}} \theta, \quad (17a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{j=1}^K p_{ij} h_{ij} \leq \theta \cdot \sigma^2, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (17b)$$

$$r_i \geq r_{o,i}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (17c)$$

$$p_{ij} \geq 0, \quad x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (17d)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N x_{ij} \leq 1, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (17e)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^K p_{ij} \leq P_{\max,i}^{\text{UL}}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (17f)$$

where $x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$ denotes the allocation of SC j to user i , p_{ij} the transmit power on that SC, and the scalar $\theta = \sum_j h_{ij} p_{ij} / \sigma^2$. Constraint (17b) ensures equal received SNR across users, (17c) enforces user-specific rate targets $r_{o,i}$, and (17f) enforces the per-user transmit power budget $P_{\max,i}^{\text{UL}}$. Unlike the DL formulation in (2) where Lagrangian dual decomposition decouples users and yields analytical power allocation, the equal-SNR constraint (17b) introduces cross-user coupling that precludes such decomposition even if x_{ij} is relaxed to $x_{ij} \in [0, 1]$. We therefore adopt a two-stage approach: (i) SC assignment, initialized from the DL DPA and exploiting TDD channel reciprocity, followed by (ii) power optimization for fixed SCs, with iterative SC reallocation via Algorithm 1 to reduce total transmit power. As in the DL, we develop differentiated and equal power allocation strategies.

A. DIFFERENTIATED POWER ALLOCATION

To solve (17), we begin with a fixed SC allocation x_{ij} obtained from the DL DPA procedure in Section IV-A. In TDD systems, channel reciprocity ensures that the UL and DL channels experience identical propagation conditions within the coherence time, i.e., $h_{ij}^{\text{UL}} = h_{ij}^{\text{DL}} \triangleq h_{ij}$. This property motivates initializing the UL SC assignment from the DL optimization framework. Specifically, we solve the DL DPA problem using the UL rate requirements $r_{o,i}^{\text{UL}}$, and interpreting the power budget as the aggregate UL power $p_{ij} = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i$.

With fixed $\mathcal{J} = \{j : x_{ij} = 1\}$, problem (17) decomposes into individual per-user optimizations:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{p}} \quad & \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} \frac{h_j}{\sigma^2} p_j, \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & r \geq r_o, \quad p_j \geq 0, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Solving (18) via Lagrangian dual decomposition yields the classical water-filling-type solution

$$p_j^* = \frac{\sigma^2}{h_j} \left[\frac{\lambda B}{\beta \ln 2} - 1 \right]^+, \quad (19)$$

where the optimal dual variable $\lambda^* = \frac{\ln 2}{\beta B} 2^{\frac{r_o}{B|\mathcal{J}|}}$ is chosen so that $r = r_o$ and depends on the number of SCs $|\mathcal{J}|$ assigned

to the user. After computing p_j^* for all users, we scale each user's total power so that all achieve a common received SNR, setting $\theta = \max_i \theta_i$. Users whose received SNR exceeds θ will relinquish SCs, which are reassigned using similar SC reallocation strategy as in Algorithm 1 to reduce overall transmit power while preserving rate feasibility.

B. EQUAL POWER ALLOCATION

Under EPA, each user transmits using a uniform power p across its SCs \mathcal{J} . For a fixed SC allocation x_{ij} (again initialized from the DL DPA assignment), the per-user problem becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_p \quad & p \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} \frac{h_j}{\sigma^2}, \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & r \geq r_o, \quad p \geq 0, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The achievable rate expression is transcendental in p , so a closed-form solution for p^* does not exist in general. We therefore determine p^* by bisection. In the high-SNR regime, the $+1$ term in (1) can be neglected, leading to a closed-form approximation for p^* , which is used as an initial guess for the bisection search.

Once a feasible set $\{p^*\}$ is obtained, we again enforce the equal-SNR constraint by scaling user powers to a common target θ and invoking SC reallocation as in Algorithm 1 to iteratively redistribute SCs. As in the UL DPA case, SCs are moved from users with surplus received SNR (and margin w.r.t. $r_{o,i}$) to users that are rate-limited, with power re-optimization after each reallocation. This yields a UL configuration that meets all rate constraints, equalizes received SNR for robust ADC operation, and reduces total transmit power under the simpler EPA structure.

VI. ADMISSION CONTROL

When total power requirements exceed available budgets, admission control becomes necessary. In the DL, we leverage the Lagrange multipliers λ from the optimization problem, where each λ_i reflects the sensitivity of the total power to the corresponding rate constraint. Users with higher values of λ_i are prioritized for rate reduction. In the UL, we first reduce CL slice rates. If infeasibility persists, users are preemptively dropped starting from the CL slice to preserve service continuity for higher-priority applications.

A. DOWNLINK RATE ADJUSTMENT

From the duality principle [31], each Lagrange multiplier λ_i in problem (2) represents the power sensitivity to the target rate:

$$\lambda_i = \frac{\partial p^*}{\partial r_{o,i}} \quad (21)$$

where p^* is the optimal total DL power. Since the objective function in (2) is convex with respect to the constraints, the rate reduction algorithm can use the well-known Newton-Raphson method [42] to iteratively compute the discrepancy

between available and required power using λ . The total power differential is:

$$dp^* = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_c} \lambda_i dr_{o,i} + \sum_{i \notin \mathcal{S}_c} \lambda_i dr_{o,i}, \quad (22)$$

where \mathcal{S}_c is the set of CL slice. Since only the rates of CL slice users are adjusted ($dr_{o,i} = 0$, for $i \notin \mathcal{S}_c$), the power change approximation becomes:

$$\Delta p^* \approx \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_c} \lambda_i \Delta r_{o,i}, \quad (23)$$

To reduce power while preserving the CL slice sum rate C , we exploit the heterogeneous power sensitivities among users. After sorting CL users by descending λ_i values, we iteratively transfer rate from the most power-sensitive user (highest, λ_1) to others. The redistribution weights $1/\lambda_i^\delta$, favor power-efficient users, with $\delta \geq 1$ controlling the bias strength.

Let $\Delta r_{1,n}$ denote the rate reduction for user 1 in iteration n . Each user $i \in \mathcal{S}_c \setminus \{1\}$ receives:

$$\Delta r_{i,n} = \frac{\Delta r_{1,n}}{\lambda_i^\delta} \left(\sum_{j=2}^{|\mathcal{S}_c|} \frac{1}{\lambda_j^\delta} \right)^{-1} \quad (24)$$

Substituting into (23) and solving for the required power reduction $\Delta p_n = p - p^{\max}$ yields:

$$\Delta p_n = \lambda_1 \Delta r_{1,n} - \sum_{i=2}^{|\mathcal{S}_c|} \lambda_i \Delta r_{i,n} \quad (25)$$

and

$$\Delta r_{1,n} = \frac{\Delta p_n}{\lambda_1 - \frac{\sum_{i=2}^{|\mathcal{S}_c|} 1/\lambda_i^{\delta-1}}{\sum_{i=2}^{|\mathcal{S}_c|} 1/\lambda_i^\delta}} \quad (26)$$

Then the rate updates becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} r_{o,1,n+1} &= \max(r_{o,1,n} - \Delta r_{1,n}, 0), \\ r_{o,i,n+1} &= r_{o,i,n} + \frac{\min(\Delta r_{1,n}, r_{o,1,n})}{\lambda_i^\delta \sum_{i=2}^{|\mathcal{S}_c|} \frac{1}{\lambda_i^\delta}}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{S}_c \setminus \{1\} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

The parameter δ controls redistribution: when $\delta = 1$, rates are redistributed proportionally to $1/\lambda_i$, providing moderate bias; as $\delta \rightarrow \infty$, all excess rate goes to the user with minimum λ , maximizing power efficiency. Algorithm 2 implements this iterative process, re-solving problem (2) after each rate update until $p \leq p^{\max}$. If this reallocation strategy fails to yield the desired reduction in p^{\max} and exhibits an oscillatory (or bouncing) behavior across users, it may signal the infeasibility of further improvement under current constraints—necessitating either a global reduction in the rate target of the CL slice as in [29] or CL user removal.

Although the above derivation uses Lagrange multipliers from the convex optimization problem (DPA case), the rate adjustment algorithm 2 remains valid for EPA. Now the

Algorithm 2 DL Rate Adjustment - CL Sum Rate Preserved

```

1: Input:  $r_{o,i} \forall i \in \mathcal{S}_c, \epsilon, p^{\max}, \delta$ 
2: Output:  $r_{o,i} \forall i \in \mathcal{S}_c, p_{ij}$ 
3: Solve DL optimization (2)  $\rightarrow$  update  $p_{ij}, \lambda$ 
4:  $p = \sum_{i,j} p_{ij}$ 
5: while  $p > p^{\max} - \epsilon$  do
6:   Sort CL users in descending order of  $\lambda_i$ 
7:   Identify top user:  $\lambda_1$ , with rate  $r_{o,1}$ 
8:   Compute  $\Delta r_1 = (p - p^{\max}) \left( \lambda_1 - \frac{\sum_{i=2}^{|\mathcal{S}_c|} 1/\lambda_i^{\delta-1}}{\sum_{i=2}^{|\mathcal{S}_c|} 1/\lambda_i^\delta} \right)^{-1}$ 
9:    $r_{o,1} \leftarrow \max(r_{o,1} - \Delta r_1, 0)$ 
10:  for each  $i \in \mathcal{S}_c \setminus \{1\}$  do
11:     $r_{o,i} \leftarrow r_{o,i} + \min(\Delta r_1, r_{o,1}) \left( \lambda_i^\delta \sum_{j=2}^{|\mathcal{S}_c|} 1/\lambda_j^\delta \right)^{-1}$ 
12:  end for
13:  Solve DL optimization (2) and update  $p_{ij}, \lambda, p$ 
14: end while

```

power sensitivity $\tilde{\lambda}_i$ is computed directly from the Shannon capacity formula with equal power p allocated to the SCs:

$$\tilde{\lambda}_i = \frac{\partial p_i^*}{\partial r_{o,i}} = \frac{\ln 2}{\beta_i B} \left(\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \frac{h_{ij}}{\sigma^2 + \beta_i p h_{ij}} \right)^{-1}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{S}_c \quad (28)$$

where \mathcal{J}_i is the set of SCs allocated to user i .

B. UPLINK RATE ADJUSTMENT

In the UL, admission control is triggered when any user violates its individual power constraint p_i^{\max} . The UL optimization decomposes per user for fixed SC allocation \mathcal{J}_i . The dual variable $\lambda_i^* = \partial p_i^* / \partial r_{o,i}$ reflects only the local marginal power increase with respect to target rate, so $\Delta p_i^* \approx \lambda_i^* \Delta r_{o,i}$. Although λ_i does not admit a global interpretation across slices, it provides a consistent ranking of CL users by power efficiency and can be used to guide rate adaptation.

We adopt a hierarchical strategy. First, CL users reduce rates according to:

$$\Delta r_{o,i} = \chi \cdot \frac{\lambda_i}{\sum_{m \in \mathcal{S}_c} \lambda_m} \cdot \frac{(p_i - p_i^{\max})^+}{p_i^{\max}}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{S}_c, \quad (29)$$

where χ is a scaling parameter and \mathcal{S}_c the set of CL slice. This penalizes power-expensive users (high λ_i) while preserving slice fairness. After each update, UL power allocation is re-optimized and SCs are redistributed from rate-excess to rate-deficit users, exploiting frequency diversity. If power violations persist, users are progressively removed starting from CL, then URLLC if necessary. Algorithm 3 summarizes this procedure.

VII. DYNAMIC TIME DIVISION DUPLEXING

In private 5G networks, we employ non-frequency reuse cell deployment to eliminate inter-cell interference and achieve ultra-reliable performance [43]. This architecture enables each cell to configure its TDD split independently without

Algorithm 3 UL Admission Control

```

1: Input:  $r_{o,i}, p_i^{\max}, \mathcal{J}_i \forall i, \epsilon$ , scaling  $\chi$ 
2: Output:  $r_{o,i}, \mathcal{J}_i, p_{ij}$ 
3: Solve UL optimization (18)  $\rightarrow$  update  $p_i, \lambda_i \forall i$ 
4: while  $\exists i : p_i > p_i^{\max} + \epsilon$  do
5:   if  $|\mathcal{S}_c| > 0$  then
6:     for  $i \in \mathcal{S}_c$  do
7:        $r_{o,i} \leftarrow \max(r_{o,i} - \Delta r_{o,i}, 0)$  via (29)
8:     end for
9:     Solve UL optimization (18)  $\rightarrow$  update  $p_i, \lambda_i \forall i$ 
10:    Reallocate SCs using Algorithm 1
11:  end if
12:  if no power improvement or  $|\mathcal{S}_c| = 0$  then
13:    Drop user with largest power violation (CL users
    first, then URLLC users)
14:  end if
15: end while
    
```

requiring inter-cell coordination and allows dynamic adjustment based on real-time traffic demands.

Let η denote the fraction of time allocated to DL, and $1 - \eta$ the UL fraction. The effective rate constraints become:

$$r_i^{DL} \geq \frac{r_{o,i}^{DL}}{\eta}, \quad r_i^{UL} \geq \frac{r_{o,i}^{UL}}{1 - \eta}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (30)$$

When one direction approaches power limits while the other has surplus capacity, adjusting η can restore feasibility without degrading QoS. We derive the optimal time split using sensitivity analysis based on Lagrange multipliers.

For the power-constrained DL, the power sensitivity to time allocation is:

$$\frac{\partial p^{DL*}}{\partial \eta} = -\frac{1}{\eta^2} \sum_i r_{o,i}^{DL} \lambda_i^{DL*} \quad (31)$$

Using Newton-Raphson, the iterative update for DL power excess $\Delta p^{DL} = p^{DL} - p_{\max}^{DL}$ is:

$$\Delta \eta = \frac{\Delta p^{DL} \cdot \eta^2}{\sum_i r_{o,i}^{DL} \lambda_i^{DL}} \quad (32)$$

Similarly, for UL power excess:

$$\Delta \eta = -\frac{\Delta p^{UL} \cdot (1 - \eta)^2}{\sum_i r_{o,i}^{UL} \lambda_i^{UL}} \quad (33)$$

Algorithm 4 implements this adaptive mechanism, first attempting time reallocation before invoking admission control from Section VI.

VIII. SIMULATION RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. FACTORY ENVIRONMENT AND SYSTEM PARAMETERS

For evaluation, we consider a $97 \times 36 \text{ m}^2$ factory zone comprising concrete walls and columns, dense metallic storage racks, wooden boxes and doors, and glass windows. This heterogeneous environment generates complex multipath propagation through reflections, diffractions, and scattering—

Algorithm 4 Dynamic TDD Time Split Adjustment

```

1: Input:  $r_{o,i}^{DL}, r_{o,i}^{UL} \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \epsilon, \eta, p_{\max}^{DL}, p_{\max}^{UL}$ 
2: Output: Updated  $\eta, r_{o,i}, p_{ij}$ 
3: Solve DL problem (2)  $\rightarrow p_{ij}^{DL}, \lambda_i^{DL}$ 
4: Solve UL problem (18)  $\rightarrow p_i^{UL}, \lambda_i^{UL}$ 
5: Compute  $p^{DL} = \sum_{i,j} p_{ij}^{DL}, p^{UL} = \sum_j p_j^{UL}$ 
6: while  $p^{DL} > p_{\max}^{DL} - \epsilon$  and  $p^{UL} < p_{\max}^{UL} - \epsilon$  do  $\triangleright$  DL
    power limited
7:    $\eta \leftarrow \eta + \frac{(p^{DL} - p_{\max}^{DL})\eta^2}{\sum_i r_{o,i}^{DL} \lambda_i^{DL}}$ 
8:   Re-solve DL/UL optimization with updated  $\eta$ 
9: end while
10: if  $p^{DL} > p_{\max}^{DL} - \epsilon$  and  $p^{UL} = p_{\max}^{UL} - \epsilon$  then  $\triangleright$  DL
    still infeasible
11:   Apply DL admission control (Section VI.A)
12: end if
13: while  $p^{UL} > p_{\max}^{UL} - \epsilon$  and  $p^{DL} < p_{\max}^{DL} - \epsilon$  do  $\triangleright$  UL
    power limited
14:    $\eta \leftarrow \eta - \frac{(p^{UL} - p_{\max}^{UL})(1 - \eta)^2}{\sum_i r_{o,i}^{UL} \lambda_i^{UL}}$ 
15:   Re-solve DL/UL optimization with updated  $\eta$ 
16: end while
17: if  $p^{UL} > p_{\max}^{UL} - \epsilon$  and  $p^{DL} = p_{\max}^{DL} - \epsilon$  then  $\triangleright$  UL
    still infeasible
18:   Apply UL admission control (Section VI.B)
19: end if
20: if  $p^{UL} > p_{\max}^{UL} - \epsilon$  and  $p^{DL} > p_{\max}^{DL} - \epsilon$  then  $\triangleright$ 
    Both UL and DL are power limited
21:   Apply DL and UL admission control (Section VI)
22: end if
    
```

conditions essential for validating the proposed slice-aware RA algorithms under realistic industrial channels.

Channel modeling employs the Volcano Flex ray-tracing engine configured for two reflections and one diffraction, with unlimited transmissions through dielectric materials. This configuration balances computational efficiency with accuracy in capturing dominant propagation mechanisms. The engine computes frequency-selective channel coefficients for the 106 SCs (180 kHz spacing, matching 5G numerology 0) across 20 MHz bandwidth at 3.7 GHz carrier frequency, providing the high-resolution channel characterization necessary for RA optimization.

Table 1 summarizes the electromagnetic (EM) properties of building materials, derived from ITU-R P.1238-7 [35]. Conductivity follows $\sigma = c f^d$ with frequency f in GHz and the constants c and d given in ITU-R P.1238-7. These parameters directly determine path loss and fading characteristics: concrete structures exhibit moderate conductivity ($\sigma = 0.094 \text{ S/m}$) and permittivity ($\epsilon_r = 5.31$), causing significant attenuation; metallic racks ($\sigma = 10^7 \text{ S/m}$) produce strong specular reflections that dominate multipath profiles; wooden elements allow partial transmission with moderate loss; and glass windows create both transmission and reflection paths.

TABLE 1. Building materials, thickness, and EM properties at $f=3.7$ GHz

Name	Material	Thickness (cm)	σ (S/m)	ϵ_r
Columns	Concrete	20	0.0940	5.31
Walls	Concrete	20		
Storage Boxes	Wood	7.5	0.0191	1.99
Internal Doors	Wood	6		
Storage Racks	Metal	1	10^7	1.00
Windows	Glass	1	0.0205	6.27

As shown in Figure 3, a single omnidirectional base station operating in SISO mode is positioned at 5 m height with 1 m wall clearance. The BS serves users distributed on an 850-point grid with 2 m spacing (0.25 UE/m²), with all UEs at 1.5 m height corresponding to the placement of typical industrial equipment. The comprehensive channel data set [33] encompasses measurements from 15 dual-polarized BS locations, from which we extract SISO configurations by selecting the corresponding single-antenna elements.

FIGURE 3. Study area with the BS (yellow) and 850 possible UEs (red).

Tables 2 and 3 summarize the simulation parameters and slice-specific QoS requirements. Each scheduling period spans 5 ms. We conduct 1000 Monte Carlo trials, randomly selecting N active users from the 850-location grid per trial. This sample size ensures statistical significance while capturing the full range of propagation conditions—from line-of-sight paths near the BS to severe multipath fading in areas shadowed by metallic racks.

B. BENCHMARKS

We compare the performance of the proposed UL and DL slice-aware resource optimization methods with the following benchmark schemes.

1) Successive Convex Approximation-Based Scheme – Downlink Baseline

We implement a benchmark based on the joint power and SC allocation framework proposed in [15], which combines a Big-M mixed-integer formulation with a Successive Convex Approximation (SCA) routine. The objective is to minimize the total transmit power while satisfying per-user rate requirements through continuous relaxations of binary SC assignments. This approach is adapted to a single-numerology

TABLE 2. Simulation parameters

Parameters	Values
Carrier frequency, f	3.7 GHz
Antenna gains	$G_t = G_u = 0$ dBi
Noise spectral density	-174 dBm/Hz
Total bandwidth, B_w	20 MHz
Subchannel bandwidth, B	180 kHz
Numerology 0	15 kHz SCS
Number of subchannels, K	106
Cell radius	200 m
BS height	5 m
UE height	1.5 m
BS transmit power	26 dBm
CL slice UE transmit power	23 dBm
URLLC slice UE transmit power	26 dBm
TS slice UE transmit power	17 dBm

TABLE 3. Per slice QoS specifications and number of active users under normal and congested conditions

Slice	Requirements	Normal Conditions		Congestion Conditions	
		Target Rate	UE Count	Target Rate	UE Count
URLLC	$\gamma_s = 99.999\%$ $a_s = 2$ Mbps $D_s^{\max} = 10$ ms $J_s = 2$ ms $T_f = 1$ ms $\eta = 0.7$	10 Mbps	2	100 Mbps	4
TS	$L = 550$ B, $T_f = 1$ ms	4.4 Mbps	1	8.8 Mbps	2
CL	$C = 10$ Mbps	10 Mbps	5	100 Mbps	10

DL scenario using the same channel realizations, per-slice QoS requirements, and user parameters as in our proposed schemes.

At each SCA iteration, the following convex subproblem is solved:

$$\min_{\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{s}} \sum_{ij} p_{ij} - \kappa \sum_{i,j} (1 - 2x_{ij}^{(t)}) x_{ij} + v \sum_i s_i, \quad (34a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } r_i(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}) + s_i \geq r_{o,i}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (34b)$$

$$0 \leq p_{ij} \leq P_{\max} x_{ij}, \quad \forall i, j, \quad (34c)$$

$$\sum_i x_{ij} = 1, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (34d)$$

$$0 \leq x_{ij} \leq 1, \quad s_i \geq 0, \quad \forall i, j. \quad (34e)$$

Here, p_{ij} and x_{ij} denote the transmit power and fractional SC assignment of user i on SC j . The binary constraint $x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$ is relaxed to $x_{i,j} \in [0, 1]$, and a difference-of-convex (DC) penalty term $-\kappa \sum_{i,j} (x_{ij} - x_{ij}^2)$ is introduced to encourage binary solutions. Its concave part $-x_{ij}^2$ is linearized at $x_{ij}^{(t)}$, yielding the convexified form in (34a). The coupling constraint $p_{ij} \leq P_{\max} x_{ij}$ ensures power is allocated only on active SCs, and the slack variables s_i penalize minor infeasibilities. Each convex subproblem is solved using CVX (SDPT3) until convergence of total

transmit power, producing a near-binary allocation x_{ij}^* that eliminates the need for post-processing.

2) Greedy Rate-Deficit Scheme – Uplink Baseline

In this baseline, each SC is greedily assigned to the user that achieves the largest reduction in its instantaneous rate deficit $(r_{o,i} - r_i)^+$ under water-filling power allocation. The principle of allocating resources proportional to users' QoS or rate requirements has been extensively studied in multiuser OFDMA systems [44]–[46], while QoS-driven greedy resource allocation for UL communications has been explored in [47], [48]. Unlike classical maximum-rate SC allocation that prioritizes users with the strongest channels, the greedy rate-deficit rule dynamically favors users whose achieved rates fall below their target rates, effectively balancing fairness and throughput. This design provides a meaningful baseline for comparison with our proposed UL schemes, which aim to meet the respective QoS requirements of all users per slice.

Each user $i \in \mathcal{N}$ is assigned a target-proportional integer quota:

$$q_i = \left\lfloor K \frac{r_{o,i}}{\sum_{m \in \mathcal{N}} r_{o,m}} \right\rfloor, \quad \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} q_i = K, \quad (35)$$

where $\sum_{m \in \mathcal{N}} r_{o,m}$ represents the aggregate rate demand across all users in the system. The proportional-quota rule in (35) enforces weighted fairness similar to rate-proportional scheduling [45], [46], ensuring that users with higher QoS demands receive proportionally more SCs. When $\sum_i \lfloor K r_{o,i} / \sum_m r_{o,m} \rfloor < K$, the remaining SCs are distributed to users with the largest fractional remainders, guaranteeing $\sum_i q_i = K$ while respecting minimum quota constraints.

SCs are then allocated sequentially in random order according to the rate-deficit metric:

$$i_j^* = \arg \max_{i \in \mathcal{N}, |\mathcal{J}_i| < q_i} \left[\min(r_i^{\text{new}}, r_{o,i}) - \min(r_i^{\text{old}}, r_{o,i}) \right], \quad (36)$$

where r_i^{old} and r_i^{new} denote the achievable rates of user i before and after the tentative assignment of SC j , respectively, and \mathcal{J}_i is the current set of SCs allocated to user i . The rates are computed under per-user water-filling power allocation:

$$p_j^* = \left[\frac{B}{\lambda \ln 2} - \frac{\sigma^2}{\beta h_{ij}} \right]^+, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} p_j^* = p_i^{\text{max}}, \quad (37)$$

where $\frac{B}{\lambda \ln 2}$ denotes the water level obtained via bisection to satisfy the per-user power constraint $\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} p_j^* = p_i^{\text{max}}$, λ is the Lagrange multiplier associated with the rate constraint, and β is the modulation-specific factor accounting for BER performance as defined in (1). Equation (37) follows from maximizing (1) subject to the total per-user power budget using Lagrangian optimization. p_i^{max} denotes the maximum transmit power of user i , determined by slice type (Table 2).

At each greedy iteration, the algorithm evaluates (37) for each candidate user i with $|\mathcal{J}_i| < q_i$, computes the marginal improvement in their deficit-capped rate via (36), and assigns the current SC to the user yielding the largest gain. To enhance computational efficiency, three micro-optimizations are employed: (1) caching per-user sorted channel gains to avoid repeated sorting; (2) warm-starting the bisection search using the water level from the previous iteration; and (3) reusing r_i^{old} from cache so that each candidate user runs water-filling only once per iteration (for r_i^{new}), rather than recomputing both baseline and augmented rates.

3) Distributed/Equal Power and Hungarian-Based Subchannel Allocation – UL/DL Baseline

Inspired by the iterative Hungarian framework proposed in [49] [50] for UL resource assignment, we implement a fairness-oriented SC allocation benchmark scheme based on the Hungarian algorithm [51]. While the classical Hungarian method solves a one-to-one assignment problem, OFDMA resource allocation requires a many-to-one mapping between SCs and users. To adapt the algorithm, the K available SCs are partitioned into $\lceil K/N \rceil$ blocks (or batches), each containing N SCs. Within each block, the Hungarian algorithm is applied to determine a one-to-one SC–user assignment that minimizes the total assignment cost defined by a cost matrix. The cost associated with assigning subchannel j to user i is given by:

$$[\mathbf{W}]_{ij} = \frac{1}{h_{ij}}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, j \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (38)$$

which is equivalent to maximizing the aggregate channel gain within each batch. After the initial assignment, the algorithm iteratively rebuilds the cost matrix for the remaining SCs and re-applies the Hungarian step until all SCs are allocated, following the same iterative philosophy in [49]. This iterative batch-wise assignment ensures that each user receives approximately the same number of SCs, thereby achieving strong fairness across the user set \mathcal{N} at the expense of slightly reduced spectral efficiency compared to throughput-oriented greedy schemes.

After SC assignment, transmit power is allocated according to the DPA and EPA schemes proposed in sections IV and V, respectively. The resulting DPA/EPA and Hungarian-Based scheme is applied symmetrically in both UL and DL evaluations and serves as a fairness-driven baseline for comparison against our proposed frameworks.

C. ANALYSIS OF NUMERICAL RESULTS

Unless otherwise stated, all evaluations use mixed-slice settings in which CL, URLLC, and TS users are simultaneously active and compete for shared radio resources defined in Table 3. This reflects realistic smart-factory deployments with strong QoS heterogeneity. We compare all proposed algorithms alongside two benchmark classes: (i) Hungarian-based variants, representing traditional fairness-oriented SC

assignment, and (ii) SCA (DL) and Greedy (UL), representing classical baselines in convex and greedy RA design.

1) Power and Energy Optimization

We evaluate the RA algorithms for DL and UL under the normal operating conditions defined in Table 3 (without admission control), comparing their performance in minimizing power consumption and the energy consumed per transmitted bit.

The DL algorithms compared are summarized as follows:

- *DPA*: Optimal joint power and SC allocation
- $EPA_{x_{DL+R}}$: EPA with *DPA*-based initial SC assignment (x_{DL}) and iterative SC reallocation (R).
- $EPA_{x_{DL}}$: EPA using x_{DL} , no reallocation.
- EPA_H : EPA using Hungarian-based (H) SC assignment (*benchmark*).
- *SCA*: convex-approximation baseline (*benchmark*).

Figure 4 presents CDFs of DL performance metrics. In Figure 4(a), *DPA* achieves the lowest transmit power, with over 95% of realizations below 20 dBm, followed by $EPA_{x_{DL+R}}$ at 88%. Without SC reallocation, $EPA_{x_{DL}}$ and EPA_H reach this threshold in only 80% of cases. The *SCA* baseline underperforms in the lower half of the distribution due to its relaxation gap, yet surpasses $EPA_{x_{DL}}$ and EPA_H beyond the median, with about 85% of realizations below 20 dBm. The superior performance of *DPA* stems from its optimal water-filling strategy, which ensures that target rates are met exactly rather than exceeded. Figure 4(b) shows the corresponding energy-per-bit results. *DPA* attains a median of 16.4 pJ/bit, compared to 23.4 pJ/bit for $EPA_{x_{DL+R}}$ and above 30 pJ/bit for the remaining schemes—representing a 30% reduction relative to $EPA_{x_{DL+R}}$ and more than 45% compared to the other DL schemes.

The UL algorithms compared are summarized thus:

- $DPA_{x_{DL+R}}$: Water-filling power with x_{DL+R} initial SC assignment and reallocation.
- $EPA_{x_{DL+R}}$: EPA with x_{DL+R} SC assignment.
- DPA_H / EPA_H : *DPA*/*EPA* with H SC assignment (*benchmark*).
- Greedy: Rate-deficit SC assignment with water-filling power (*benchmark*).

The UL CDFs are shown in Figure 5. In Figure 5(a), $DPA_{x_{DL+R}}$ and $EPA_{x_{DL+R}}$ reduce the per-user transmit power by approximately 11 dB at the median relative to their Hungarian counterparts. This improvement arises from adaptive SC reallocation, which better balances the received SNR across users and prevents rate overshoot. The Greedy baseline exhausts the per-slice UE power budgets (17, 23, and 26 dBm for TS, CL, and URLLC, respectively), resulting in three distinct CDF clusters at these limits and indicating the absence of power minimization. Figure 5(b) confirms these trends: $DPA_{x_{DL+R}}$ and $EPA_{x_{DL+R}}$

FIGURE 4. CDF plots in the downlink per algorithm: (a) total required transmit power, and (b) energy per transmitted bit.

achieve approximately 85% higher median energy efficiency than the Hungarian variants, whereas the Greedy baseline exhibits a median energy consumption in the nJ/bit regime, corresponding to an order-of-magnitude degradation in energy efficiency relative to the proposed schemes.

2) Admission Control and Dynamic Time Division Duplexing

We evaluate the admission control mechanism under network congestion by scaling both user density and slice-specific demands according to Table 3. Figures 6(a) and 7(a) show that the proposed strategy successfully constrains transmission power within the BS and UE power budgets for DL and UL, respectively. The required BS transmit power in the DL under *DPA* and *EPA* is shown in Figure 6(a). Due to the inherent power penalty of uniform per-SC allocation (see Figures 4–5), *EPA* reaches the power budget more frequently, thereby triggering admission control in approximately 40% of DL realizations compared to 17% under *DPA*. In the UL, Figure 7(a) shows that *EPA* reaches the per-user power limits only marginally more often than *DPA*. This is expected since the equal-SNR constraint inherently limits large power disparities across users.

FIGURE 5. CDF plots in the uplink per algorithm: per user (a) transmit power, and (b) energy per transmitted bit.

FIGURE 6. CDF evaluations: (a) BS transmit power with admission control in the downlink, (b) User drop for different values of δ .

The impact of the redistribution bias parameter δ on system performance is shown in Figure 6(b), evaluated under DPA. Higher δ values moderately reduce user drops by allocating more excess rate Δr_1 to users with lower power sensitivity (smaller λ_i), thus improving power efficiency.

To examine dynamic TDD adaptation under asymmetric traffic, we introduce load ratio ψ where $r_{o,i}^{DL} = \psi \cdot r_{o,i}^{UL}$. Figure 7(b) illustrates how the duplexing ratio η responds to varying ψ , evaluated under DPA. For $\psi < 1$ (UL-heavy traffic), η decreases below 0.5, allocating more time to UL. Conversely, $\psi > 1$ (DL-heavy traffic) increases η to accommodate DL demands. The distribution tails contain outliers from Monte Carlo trials where severe channel conditions cause both links to reach power limits simultaneously. In these cases, time reallocation alone cannot restore feasibility instead, admission control for rate reduction or user removal is triggered.

3) Impact of Frame Duration and TDD Configuration on URLLC Reliability

The delay violation probability under framed TDD transmission depends critically on the interplay between the TDD frame duration T_f , the delay bound D_i^{\max} , the allocated service rate $r_{o,i}$, and the duplexing ratio η . Figures 8(a)–(b) characterize these dependencies and delineate the feasible

operating regions for URLLC slice provisioning. The results in these figures correspond to the outage probability in the transmission direction of interest, which is assumed to be the DL without loss of generality. The corresponding UL results are obtained by symmetry through exchanging η and $1 - \eta$.

Figure 8(a) plots the outage probability versus the normalized frame duration T_f/D^{\max} for several rate ratios r_o/a at fixed $\eta = 0.7$. A sharp transition occurs at $T_f = D^{\max}$, separating two qualitatively distinct regimes. In the feasible region ($T_f < D^{\max}$), increasing the rate ratio r_o/a yields exponential reductions in outage probability, enabling stringent reliability targets such as $\gamma = 0.99999$ (outage 10^{-5}). For example, at $T_f/D^{\max} = 0.5$, increasing r_o/a from 1.5 to 5 improves outage probability by nearly four orders of magnitude.

The packing parameter $\omega_i = r_{o,i}\eta T_f/\bar{L}_i$ governs TDD fragmentation by quantifying how many average-sized packets fit within a single transmission phase. Since ω_i varies with both T_f and r_o , its impact is illustrated via $\omega = 1$ markers on each curve. This threshold is not an optimality criterion but rather a physically meaningful reference point. $\omega_i = 1$ corresponds to the regime where an average packet exactly fills one transmission phase. For $\omega_i < 1$ (left of markers), packets frequently span multiple phases, incurring inter-phase waiting times that elevate outage probability. For $\omega_i > 1$ (right of markers), corresponds to an increasingly

FIGURE 7. CDF evaluations: (a) users transmit power with admission control per slice type in the uplink, and (b) distribution of η for different values of ψ .

phase-contained transmission, yielding steeper outage curves with reduced TDD penalty.

In the saturation region ($T_f \geq D^{\max}$), the outage probability converges to the synchronization floor $1 - D^{\max}/T_f$, shown by the green dotted curve. This floor represents an irreducible lower bound imposed solely by frame-level synchronization: packets arriving in the interval $(T_f - D_i^{\max}, T_f]$ violate the delay bound regardless of the allocated service rate. Consequently, the condition $T_f < D_i^{\max}$ is a hard feasibility requirement for URLLC operation. Operating close to this boundary induces a sharp “rate cliff,” where the required service rate grows dramatically with marginal reductions in T_f/D^{\max} . In practice, reliable URLLC provisioning therefore requires $T_f \ll D^{\max}$.

Figure 8(b) isolates the TDD configuration impact by fixing $r_o/a = 4$ and varying the duplexing ratio $\eta \in \{0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9\}$. The black dashed curve represents the framed-only baseline without UL/DL gaps—the idealized case where every frame serves the transmission direction of interest. The results show that η has a substantial effect on achievable reliability. At $T_f/D^{\max} = 0.5$, increasing η from 0.2 to 0.9 improves outage probability by nearly two orders of magnitude. For small η (e.g., 0.2 and 0.3), the curves exhibit mild non-smooth variations as T_f increases; this behavior is a direct consequence of the discrete nature

of TDD fragmentation, whereby the integer number of inter-phase gaps experienced by a packet changes as T_f varies, leading to piecewise transitions in the delay distribution.

Two mechanisms drive the improvement with increasing η : (i) larger η raises ω_i , reducing the likelihood of packet fragmentation across multiple transmission phases; and (ii) it shortens the inter-phase gap $\tau = (1 - \eta)T_f$, decreasing the delay penalty incurred by fragmented packets. The vertical gap between TDD curves and the framed-only baseline quantifies the TDD tax—the performance penalty from alternating UL/DL transmission. This penalty is most severe at small η and vanishes as $\eta \rightarrow 1$.

The combined insights yield the following design guidelines:

- **Frame duration constraint:** Maintain $T_f < D_i^{\max}$ with margin; operating near $T_f \approx D_i^{\max}$ triggers the synchronization-limited regime and explosive rate requirements.
- **Packing parameter target:** Design for $\omega_i \gtrsim 1$ so most packets complete within one or two phases; $\omega_i \ll 1$ renders TDD fundamentally inefficient for URLLC.
- **TDD configuration:** Align η with traffic asymmetry—DL-centric applications favor DL-heavy patterns (e.g., DDDSU, $\eta \approx 0.7$), while UL-centric applications require UL-heavy configurations. Small η dramatically inflates rate requirements.
- **Rate–TDD trade-off:** The TDD tax can be offset by increasing $r_{o,i}$ (higher power/bandwidth) or η (reduced opposite-direction capacity). System design must balance these levers based on slice priorities and resource constraints.

D. COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS

Table 4 summarizes the computational complexity of the proposed slice-aware RA algorithms and baseline methods, where N denotes the number of users, K the number of SCs, ε convergence tolerance, and I the number of iterative updates.

In the DL, the complexity of the proposed algorithms spans from $\mathcal{O}(NK \log(1/\varepsilon))$ for EPA_{xDL} to $\mathcal{O}(NK + N^2 \log(1/\varepsilon) + N \log N + K \log K)$ for DPA, where the additional logarithmic terms arise from per-user updates and SC reallocation. While DPA achieves optimal power and SC allocation, its quadratic scaling in N limits scalability to small-to-moderate network sizes. EPA_{xDL} remains the most computationally efficient for resource-constrained deployments, whereas EPA_{xDL+R} achieves a near-optimal trade-off by introducing an iterative reallocation step at $\mathcal{O}(NK + K \log(1/\varepsilon))$. The SCA-based baseline exhibits higher computational demand at $\mathcal{O}(I \cdot NK^2)$, where I typically ranges between 5 and 7. Its quadratic dependence on K comes from solving successive convex approximations with coupled power–SC variables, which require second-order

FIGURE 8. Delay violation probability under framed TDD transmission: (a) effect of rate ratio r_o/a at fixed $\eta = 0.7$; (b) effect of duplexing ratio η at fixed $r_o/a = 4$, with the framed-only (no UL/DL gaps) baseline. Filled circles mark $\omega = 1$, delineating fragmentation-dominated operation (left) from efficient single-phase transmission (right).

cone programs (SOCP) with NK variables per iteration—rendering it impractical for systems with $K > 100$.

The proposed UL algorithms leverage closed-form power updates, resulting in significantly lower computational cost overall. DPA_{xDL+R} achieves high efficiency with a dominant complexity of $\mathcal{O}(NK)$, complemented by additional lightweight overhead from user sorting and SC reallocation, yielding an overall bound of $\mathcal{O}(NK + N \log N + K \log K)$. This linear scaling in N and K enables practical real-time implementation even in wideband settings. In contrast, the greedy baseline evaluates WF solutions for all candidate users at each SC, leading to a worst-case complexity of $\mathcal{O}(NK^2 \log(1/\epsilon))$, which simplifies to $\mathcal{O}(K^2 \log(1/\epsilon))$ under balanced quotas. The Hungarian-based variants remain the most demanding, scaling as $\mathcal{O}(KN^2)$, and are suitable only when fairness outweighs real-time constraints.

The access control mechanisms introduce only marginal overhead relative to the main allocation procedures. Admission control operates at $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$ through user sorting and rate redistribution, while dynamic TDD optimization adds a moderate $\mathcal{O}(I \cdot NK \log(1/\epsilon))$ cost for EPA-based variants or

$\mathcal{O}(I \cdot (NK + N^2 \log(1/\epsilon)))$ for DPA-based configurations. These access control components are lightweight compared to the primary allocation loops, ensuring that the overall framework remains computationally tractable.

E. RUNTIME AND SCALABILITY ANALYSIS

We validated the theoretical complexity in Table 4 through Monte Carlo runtime evaluations across 10^3 channel realizations. The experiments varied (i) the number of SCs $K \in \{25, 79, 106\}$ with fixed per-slice users $N = [1, 2, 5]$, and (ii) the total UEs using slice configurations $[1, 1, 2]$, $[1, 2, 5]$, and $[2, 4, 10]$ with fixed $K = 106$. All algorithms were implemented in MATLAB R2024b using vectorized operations, warm-started solvers, and precomputed Siradel channel traces, and executed in single-threaded mode on a 1.7 GHz AMD Ryzen 7 PRO 4750U processor. Median runtimes with 10th–90th percentile intervals are reported. Figures 9 and 10 show scalability results in log scale.

In the DL, DPA exhibits longer runtimes than the EPA variants due to its ellipsoid-based dual updates combined with Newton–Raphson steps, which scale superlinearly with both N and K . EPA_{xDL} and EPA_H exhibit the best scalability, showing near-linear growth consistent with their $\mathcal{O}(NK \log(1/\epsilon))$ complexity. EPA_{xDL+R} is slower because its outer reallocation passes repeatedly adjust subcarrier assignments—these loops do not affect the asymptotic order but increase constant factors and noticeably inflate runtime. The SCA baseline shows the poorest scalability, with runtimes increasing sharply for wideband cases ($K > 100$), aligning with its $\mathcal{O}(I \cdot NK^2)$ cost and the heavy SOCP solves required at each iteration.

In the UL, DPA_H is the fastest method, as it performs only a single closed-form power update on a fixed Hungarian assignment. Its EPA counterpart (EPA_H) is slower due to per-user bisection-based power updates. Both DPA_{xDL+R} and EPA_{xDL+R} incur additional runtime from repeated reallocation passes between rate-excess and rate-deficient users, which increases constant factors even though their asymptotic orders remain linear. The greedy water-filling baseline also scales poorly at large K , as it performs a water-filling evaluation for every user–SC pair. Among all UL methods, EPA_{xDL+R} is the slowest because it combines bisection-based power updates with iterative reallocation.

The empirical results thus align with theoretical predictions: EPA and DPA maintain quasi-linear scalability, with non-reallocation variants (DPA_H , EPA_{xDL} , EPA_H) offering the fastest runtimes. Reallocation-based methods (DPA_{xDL+R} , EPA_{xDL+R}) show modestly higher runtimes due to additional iterative passes, trading compute time for improved performance and QoS satisfaction. Despite MATLAB-level optimizations reducing absolute timing gaps, the observed trends match the complexity analysis, confirming the tractability of the proposed slice-aware algorithms.

TABLE 4. Computational Complexity of the UL and DL Algorithms

Category	Algorithm	Complexity	Characteristics
Downlink	DPA	$\mathcal{O}(NK + N^2 \log(1/\varepsilon))$	Optimal performance; quadratic term limits scalability in large networks.
	EPA _{xDL+R}	$\mathcal{O}(NK \log(1/\varepsilon) + N \log N)$	Best complexity–performance compromise; achieves near-optimality with iterative reallocation.
	EPA _{xDL}	$\mathcal{O}(NK \log(1/\varepsilon))$	Lowest DL complexity; suitable for resource-constrained deployments.
	EPA _H	$\mathcal{O}(KN^2 + NK \log(1/\varepsilon))$	Fair SC allocation; high computational demand.
	SCA	$\mathcal{O}(I \cdot NK^2)$	Successive convex approximation with SOCP solves; complexity grows quadratically with K .
Uplink	DPA _{xDL+R}	$\mathcal{O}(NK + N \log N + K \log K)$	Most efficient UL method; closed-form power update enables real-time deployment.
	EPA _{xDL+R}	$\mathcal{O}(NK + NK \log(1/\varepsilon) + N \log N + K \log K)$	Bisection-driven refinement; moderate cost.
	DPA _H	$\mathcal{O}(KN^2 + NK)$	Hungarian-based fair assignment; high cost.
	EPA _H	$\mathcal{O}(KN^2 + N \log(1/\varepsilon))$	Fair UL allocation with bisection refinement; high cost.
	Greedy	$\mathcal{O}(NK^2 \log(1/\varepsilon))$	Requires WF evaluation for every candidate user at each SC; reduces to $\mathcal{O}(K^2 \log(1/\varepsilon))$ under balanced quotas.
Access Control	Admission Control	$\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$	Lightweight sorting and rate redistribution.
	Dynamic TDD (DPA)	$\mathcal{O}(I \cdot (NK + N^2 \log(1/\varepsilon)))$	Newton–Raphson iteration on the DPA fixed point; largest overhead in DPA-based TDD.
	Dynamic TDD (EPA)	$\mathcal{O}(I \cdot NK \log(1/\varepsilon))$	Lower-cost TDD adjustment leveraging EPA's simpler power structure.

F. LIMITATIONS OF THE PROPOSED ALGORITHMS

While the proposed slice-aware RA framework demonstrates strong theoretical and empirical performance, several practical limitations should be acknowledged.

Single-cell, SISO assumptions. All algorithms are derived under a single-cell, SISO model with no inter-cell interference or multi-antenna processing. Modern industrial deployments often involve multi-cell coordination, MIMO beamforming, and interference coupling, which can significantly alter both channel structure and rate expressions. Extending the framework to multi-cell or massive-MIMO settings will require new dual formulations and more scalable power–subcarrier update rules.

Queueing model simplification. The QoS-driven rate targets rely on an M/M/1 queue approximation. Although analytically convenient, real traffic processes frequently deviate from Poisson arrivals and exponential service times. Burstiness, correlation, or multi-class arrival processes may require alternative models (e.g., M/G/1, G/G/1, or effective-capacity formulations) for accurate latency–rate mappings.

Centralized optimization and scalability. The proposed DPA and EPA algorithms operate in a centralized manner with global CSI and rate information. Such designs may face scalability constraints in large networks due to control-plane signaling and computational load. In practice, scalable implementations may require distributed or hierarchical

decompositions in which convex steps are approximated locally, or resource assignments are coordinated through message passing.

Computational burden in real-time systems. Although asymptotically efficient, some variants (particularly those with iterative reallocation or dual updates) introduce non-negligible constant factors that may limit real-time use in high-mobility or ultra-dense deployments. Learning-assisted or warm-started predictors could accelerate convergence and reduce reliance on repeated convex subproblems.

IX. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper addressed the critical challenge of supporting heterogeneous industrial applications through effective resource allocation in sliced TDD-OFDMA network. Our framework demonstrate that transforming complex QoS requirements into rate-based constraints not only simplifies the optimization landscape but enables real-time optimization with guaranteed performance. We proposed distributed and equal power allocation algorithms for both UL and DL, complemented by admission control and dynamic TDD mechanisms to handle congestion and traffic asymmetries. Through delay violation probability analysis, we reveal fundamental design constraints for URLLC performance, power optimization, and computational efficiency, highlighting their sensitivity to scheduling granularity. Extensive simulations using factory-specific RT channel models demonstrate that our framework

FIGURE 9. Scalability analysis of the DL algorithms: Runtime vs (a) varying K with fixed N , and (b) varying N with fixed K .

achieves robust performance under harsh propagation conditions typical of industrial environments. The modular design of our framework enables flexible integration with other optimization approaches and machine learning-based control policies, providing a foundation for further enhancements.

Future work will investigate model-free, learning-based approaches that capture complex traffic dynamics without relying on restrictive arrival or service process assumptions, enabling predictive and proactive RA. The framework will also be extended to multi-cell deployments with inter-cell interference management, massive-MIMO configurations for spatial multiplexing gains, and mobility support. In parallel, distributed and sparsity-exploiting variants will be explored to reduce solver dimensionality and signaling overhead, together with online learning-assisted mechanisms capable of adapting to dynamic channel and traffic conditions. These developments are essential for real-world, large-scale, and latency-constrained industrial wireless deployments.

APPENDIX: DELAY VIOLATION PROBABILITY IN FRAMED TDD SCHEDULING

This appendix derives the delay violation probability expressions used for URLLC rate requirements in the main text. We consider two distinct time scales: the *scheduling period* T_{sp} , at which the resource allocation algorithm computes

FIGURE 10. Scalability analysis of the UL algorithms: Runtime vs (a) varying K with fixed N , and (b) varying N with fixed K .

power and SC assignments, and the *TDD frame duration* T_f , at which packets are served using these fixed allocations. Throughout, we focus on the regime $T_{sp} \gg T_f$, where a single resource allocation decision governs many TDD frame service opportunities.

A. FRAME-BASED M/M/1 SCHEDULING WITHOUT TDD PARTITIONING

Packets are served at discrete physical transmission opportunities, which we model at the TDD frame granularity T_f . Packets arriving within a frame experience a synchronization delay uniformly distributed over $[0, T_f]$, which adds to the exponential M/M/1 queuing delay.

1) Traffic Model and Service Parameter

For user i , let $a_i = \zeta_i \bar{L}_i$ denote the bit arrival rate (bits/s), where ζ_i is the packet arrival rate (packets/s) and \bar{L}_i is the mean packet size (bits/packet). Given an allocated rate $r_{o,i}$ (bits/s), the effective service parameter of the underlying M/M/1 queue is:

$$\alpha_i = \frac{r_{o,i} - a_i}{\bar{L}_i}. \quad (39)$$

Queue stability requires $r_{o,i} > a_i$, ensuring $\alpha_i > 0$.

2) Delay Distribution

The total delay D comprises queuing delay, service time, and frame synchronization delay. Because packets arriving at the queue must wait until the next frame boundary to begin service, the synchronization delay is uniformly distributed over $[0, T_f]$ and adds to the exponential M/M/1 queuing delay. This framed service model yields a piecewise delay distribution since the functional form changes depending on whether the delay argument lies within a single frame ($0 \leq D \leq T_f$) or exceeds the frame duration ($D > T_f$), where the exponential tail behavior dominates. Under the M/M/1 assumption with framed service, the PDF of D is:

$$f_D(D) = \begin{cases} 0, & D < 0, \\ \frac{1}{T_f}(1 - e^{-\alpha_i D}), & 0 \leq D \leq T_f, \\ \frac{e^{-\alpha_i D}}{T_f}(e^{\alpha_i T_f} - 1), & D > T_f. \end{cases} \quad (40)$$

Integrating (40) yields the complementary CDF (delay tail probability):

$$G_i(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x \leq 0, \\ 1 - \frac{x}{T_f} + \frac{1 - e^{-\alpha_i x}}{\alpha_i T_f}, & 0 < x \leq T_f, \\ \frac{e^{\alpha_i T_f} - 1}{\alpha_i T_f} e^{-\alpha_i x}, & x > T_f. \end{cases} \quad (41)$$

3) Delay Violation Probability and Rate Requirement

Evaluating $G_i(x)$ at $x = D_i^{\max}$ yields the exact delay violation probability:

$$\Pr\{D \geq D_i^{\max}\} = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{D_i^{\max}}{T_f} + \frac{1}{\alpha_i T_f} (1 - e^{-\alpha_i D_i^{\max}}), & \text{if } D_i^{\max} \leq T_f, \\ \frac{1}{\alpha_i T_f} (e^{\alpha_i T_f} - 1) e^{-\alpha_i D_i^{\max}}, & \text{if } D_i^{\max} > T_f. \end{cases} \quad (42)$$

A critical observation emerges: when $T_f \geq D_i^{\max}$ (first branch), the outage probability cannot fall below $1 - D_i^{\max}/T_f$ regardless of the allocated rate. This represents a fundamental saturation floor that arises from the frame synchronization delay alone. Consequently, practical URLLC deployments must satisfy $T_f < D_i^{\max}$ so that the second branch applies to enable reliability improvements through rate allocation.

For a reliability requirement γ_i (i.e., $\Pr\{D > D_i^{\max}\} \leq 1 - \gamma_i$), operating in the regime $T_f < D_i^{\max}$ yields the transcendental equation:

$$1 - \gamma_i = \frac{e^{\alpha_i T_f} - 1}{\alpha_i T_f} e^{-\alpha_i D_i^{\max}}, \quad (43)$$

which must be solved numerically (e.g., via bisection or Newton–Raphson) to obtain $\alpha_i^{(\text{frame})}$. The corresponding min-

imum rate is:

$$r_{o,i}^{(\text{frame})} = a_i + \alpha_i^{(\text{frame})} \bar{L}_i. \quad (44)$$

As $T_f \rightarrow 0$, the frame-based expression converges to the continuous-time M/M/1 result:

$$r_{o,i}^{(\text{cont})} = a_i - \frac{\bar{L}_i \ln(1 - \gamma_i)}{D_i^{\max}}. \quad (45)$$

4) Jitter Constraint

Assuming independence between queuing delay D_q and synchronization delay D_s , the total delay variance is:

$$\text{Var}\{D\} = \text{Var}\{D_q\} + \text{Var}\{D_s\} = \frac{1}{\alpha_i^2} + \frac{T_f^2}{12}, \quad (46)$$

where the first term corresponds to the exponential queuing delay and the second to the uniform frame synchronization delay. Imposing a jitter bound $\text{std}\{D\} \leq J_i$ yields:

$$\alpha_i \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{J_i^2 - T_f^2/12}}, \quad (47)$$

which is meaningful only if $J_i > T_f/\sqrt{12}$. Combining with the reliability constraint from (43), the rate requirement becomes:

$$r_{o,i}^{(\text{frame})} = a_i + \bar{L}_i \cdot \max\left(\alpha_i^{(\text{frame})}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{J_i^2 - T_f^2/12}}\right). \quad (48)$$

B. IMPACT OF TDD FRAME PARTITIONING

We now extend the analysis to account for TDD frame partitioning. Each TDD frame of duration T_f is divided into a transmission phase of duration ηT_f and an opposite-direction phase of duration $(1 - \eta)T_f$, where $\eta \in (0, 1)$ is the duplexing ratio for the transmission direction of interest, either UL or DL. When user i transmits at sustained rate $r_{o,i}$, a single transmission phase can carry up to $r_{o,i}\eta T_f$ bits. Packets exceeding this capacity must span multiple transmission phases, incurring additional UL/DL gaps.

1) Packet-Length Classes

A packet requiring exactly $(k + 1)$ transmission phases to complete must satisfy $kr_{o,i}\eta T_f < L \leq (k + 1)r_{o,i}\eta T_f$, experiencing k intervening gaps of duration $(1 - \eta)T_f$ each. Define the packet-length class:

$$A_k = \{L : kr_{o,i}\eta T_f < L \leq (k + 1)r_{o,i}\eta T_f\}, \quad (49)$$

$$k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

For exponentially distributed packet lengths with mean \bar{L}_i , the probability of class A_k is:

$$\Pr(A_k) = (1 - e^{-\omega_i}) e^{-k\omega_i}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (50)$$

where the dimensionless packing parameter is defined as:

$$\omega_i \triangleq \frac{r_{o,i}\eta T_f}{\bar{L}_i}. \quad (51)$$

This parameter measures how many average-sized packets can be transmitted per transmission phase. The class probabilities form a geometric distribution with parameter $e^{-\omega_i}$.

2) TDD-Induced Delay and Total Delay Distribution

Let $D_{0,i}$ denote the frame-based delay in the absence of TDD partitioning (with PDF given by (40) and tail $G_i(x)$ by (41)). If a packet belongs to class A_k , it experiences k inter-phase gaps of duration $\tau \triangleq (1 - \eta)T_f$ each. The total delay becomes:

$$D_i = D_{0,i} + k\tau. \quad (52)$$

The unconditional delay density for TDD-slotted transmission is:

$$f_{D_i}^{(\text{TDD})}(D) = (1 - e^{-\omega_i}) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} e^{-k\omega_i} f_{D_{0,i}}(D - k\tau). \quad (53)$$

Equation (53) reveals the ‘‘staircase’’ structure of the TDD delay distribution: shifted copies of the base framed PDF, weighted by the geometric packet-length distribution.

C. DELAY VIOLATION PROBABILITY UNDER TDD

1) TDD Outage Probability

The delay outage probability under TDD is obtained by summing over all packet-length classes:

$$\Pr\{D_i \geq D_i^{\max}\} = (1 - e^{-\omega_i}) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} e^{-k\omega_i} G_i(D_i^{\max} - k\tau), \quad (54)$$

where $G_i(\cdot)$ defined in (41) is evaluated at shifted thresholds $x_k = D_i^{\max} - k\tau$. Note that although $D_i^{\max} > 0$, the arguments x_k can become non-positive as k increases, activating the $x \leq 0$ branch of (41).

For numerical evaluation, define $m_i^* \triangleq \lfloor D_i^{\max}/\tau \rfloor$. Since $G_i(D_i^{\max} - k\tau) = 1$ for all $k \geq m_i^* + 1$, the series can be compactly written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr\{D_i \geq D_i^{\max}\} &= (1 - e^{-\omega_i}) \sum_{k=0}^{m_i^*} e^{-k\omega_i} G_i(D_i^{\max} - k\tau) + e^{-(m_i^*+1)\omega_i}. \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

When $D_i^{\max} \leq T_f$, every positive argument $x_k = D_i^{\max} - k\tau$ lies in the interval $0 < x_k \leq T_f$, so only the middle branch of (41) is active for $k = 0, \dots, m_i^*$. This corresponds to the TDD counterpart of the saturation regime where a floor exists that cannot be eliminated by increasing $r_{o,i}$. When $D_i^{\max} > T_f$, the arguments $x_k = D_i^{\max} - k\tau$ span multiple branches of (41) as k increases. We define $k_i^{(a)} \triangleq \lfloor (D_i^{\max} - T_f)/\tau \rfloor$ so that for $0 \leq k \leq k_i^{(a)}$, we have $x_k \geq T_f$ and the exponential tail branch applies; for $k_i^{(a)} + 1 \leq k \leq m_i^*$, we have $0 < x_k < T_f$ so the middle branch applies. In this regime, reliability can be improved by increasing $r_{o,i}$.

The complete TDD outage expression is given in (56).

3) Combined Rate Requirement Under TDD

For a reliability target γ_i , the unique solution $\alpha_i^{(\text{TDD})}$ is found numerically from (56). Regarding jitter, the TDD partition introduces additional delay variance because the number of inter-phase gaps k experienced by a packet is random, as it is

determined by the realized packet length, which is modeled as an exponential random variable. From (50), k follows a geometric distribution with success probability $p = 1 - e^{-\omega_i}$, yielding mean $\mathbb{E}[k] = e^{-\omega_i}/(1 - e^{-\omega_i})$ and variance:

$$\text{Var}\{k\} = \frac{e^{-\omega_i}}{(1 - e^{-\omega_i})^2}. \quad (57)$$

Since each gap contributes a fixed delay $\tau = (1 - \eta)T_f$, the variance of the TDD-induced delay component is:

$$\text{Var}\{k\tau\} = \tau^2 \text{Var}\{k\} = \tau^2 \frac{e^{-\omega_i}}{(1 - e^{-\omega_i})^2}. \quad (58)$$

For moderate-to-large ω_i (when most packets fit within a few transmission phases), this TDD-induced variance is typically small compared to the M/M/1 and frame synchronization terms. We therefore retain the frame-based jitter constraint as a good approximation. The final TDD rate requirement becomes:

$$r_{o,i} = a_i + \bar{L}_i \cdot \max\left(\alpha_i^{(\text{TDD})}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{J_i^2 - T_f^2/12}}\right). \quad (59)$$

This expression generalizes (48) to the TDD-framed setting, with $\alpha_i^{(\text{TDD})}$ obtained from the TDD-aware outage expressions. Thus, (59) is the rate requirement for URLLC users given in (4).

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$$\Pr\{D_i \geq D_i^{\max}\} = \begin{cases} \left(1 - e^{-\omega_i}\right) \sum_{k=0}^{m_i^*} e^{-k\omega_i} \left[1 - \frac{D_i^{\max} - k\tau}{T_f} + \frac{1}{\alpha_i T_f} \left(1 - e^{-\alpha_i(D_i^{\max} - k\tau)}\right)\right] + e^{-(m_i^*+1)\omega_i}, & \text{if } D_i^{\max} \leq T_f, \\ \left(1 - e^{-\omega_i}\right) \left[\sum_{k=0}^{k_i^{(a)}} e^{-k\omega_i} \frac{e^{\alpha_i T_f} - 1}{\alpha_i T_f} e^{-\alpha_i(D_i^{\max} - k\tau)} \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{k=k_i^{(a)}+1}^{m_i^*} e^{-k\omega_i} \left(1 - \frac{D_i^{\max} - k\tau}{T_f} + \frac{1}{\alpha_i T_f} \left(1 - e^{-\alpha_i(D_i^{\max} - k\tau)}\right)\right) \right] + e^{-(m_i^*+1)\omega_i}, & \text{if } D_i^{\max} > T_f. \end{cases} \quad (56)$$

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